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**EFFICACY AND SIGNIFICANCE OF PULSATING JET LAVAGE OF
THE FEMUR DURING HIP ARTHROPLASTY**

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Introduction. Hip arthroplasty has been practiced for more than half a century. During this time, endoprotheses of various shapes and designs were used. However, a number of unresolved and important issues remain, including the use of different brands of cement to fix the endoprosthesis components, different methods of femoral bone marrow lavage for better fixation of implants to the cancellous part of the femur, and, of course, the degree of saturation bone cement to reduce the risk of infection during arthroplasty.

Actuality. So far, scientists haven't fully studied the perfect method of treatment of the femoral canal intraoperatively before the use of cement fixation of implants, a brand of cement, and saturation of bone cement with antibiotics. In recent years, publications on this topic do not have a clear idea of the method and the consequences of the use of certain techniques. Therefore, further study of the treatment of the femoral canal intraoperatively before the use of cement fixation of implants is relevant.

The purpose of the work. The aim of the study was to determine the degree of effectiveness of the purification of the femur from the remnants of fat and blood by pulsating jet lavage and manual syringe lavage. The efficiency was measured by the degree of penetration of cement into the spongy part of the femur bone.

Materials and methods. A study was conducted on 30 artificial bones, which are similar in size and anatomy to humans. The study was to compare the effectiveness of fixation of the femur of the cancellous bone part depending on the method of lavage, the method of pulsating jet lavage, and manual syringe lavage of the same volume. High-pressure cementation was used in both methods.

Analysis. In all experiments, horizontal sections of the rear parts were obtained using a saw with a diamond coating. Sections were analyzed by digital image analysis to assess the penetration of cement into the spongy part of the bone.

Results. Compared to the syringe, the use of pulsating jet lavage significantly improved the penetration of cement into the cancellous bone.

Conclusions. The use of pulsating jet lavage improves the penetration of cement into the cancellous bone and should be considered a priority when performing total cement hip arthroplasty.